

The Impact of Economic Conditions on Seaport Throughput for Containerized Goods in West Africa

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Over the years, growth in the volume of West Africa's container trade has exceeded that of any other global region doubling to almost 5 million twenty-foot equivalent units (TEU). The West African maritime industry is gradually entering the world stage. International trade is effectively facilitated through improvement in transport and border efficiency, serving as a crucial factor for economic and social welfare outcomes, improving the quality of seaport services remains very important to the African continent which has been plagued with lower economic and social welfare outcomes. Therefore, the research examined the impact of economic conditions (GDP, exchange rate, interest rate, taxes, supply and demand of goods, and inflation) on the throughput for containerized goods for seaports in West Africa. The sample comprised 13 West Africa Countries and data were obtained from World Development Indicators.

The research used model to empirically re-examine long-run co-movement and the causal relationship between throughput of containerized goods and economic indicators in a regression model comprised of 13 West Africa countries from 2009-2019. The research finds that, except for the panel variance (no time effects), all other statistics significantly reject the null of no cointegration and per country basis, economic indicators have a substantially positive effect on throughput in Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, and Liberia more than half of the sampled 13 countries.

Keywords: ECONOMIC INDICATORS, CONTAINER THROUGHPUT, SEAPORTS, WEST AFRICA

Introduction

In view of the important roles in many supply chains and distribution networks relevant to international merchandise trade, seaports are also recognized as a social infrastructure. Their values are measured in this regard from the point of view of their contribution to the economy or national growth. Lee et al. (2008) posited that, in a country with a less developed seaport system, developing ports should be considered as the context of national economic security and the fundamental infrastructure of the national economy rather than commercial entities for a recovery of their scientific approaches to evaluate the impact of port development on the economy.

In recent years, container transport has turned out to be fully automated, leading to a decrease in employment (Spijkerman, 2015). Indeed, the effects of the success of a port on the country or area's economic growth appears to have an effect. However, it would also be possible for the country or area's economic development to impact the production of the seaport. Maasvlakte II was built at the port of Rotterdam due to economic growth in the region, the Netherlands and even Europe. Development was needed because of the high demand from industry and market. In general, it is not clear what direction of the relationship reigns supreme, so this is the subject of this essay.

Over the years, growth in container trade in West Africa has exceeded that of any other global region, doubling to nearly 5 million twenty-foot equivalent units (TEUs). This rise, fueled by growing sales in the area, is also leading to increased congestion at various ports (Jeremy, 2018). The West African maritime industry is steadily joining the world stage in a nut-shell. However, a range of macroeconomic and microeconomic factors, including GDP, exchange rates, interest rates, taxes, supply and demand for goods, inflation, etc., influence the economic conditions of the country (Investopedia, 2019). When the economic conditions of a nation are appalling, the capacity of containerized seaport production can never be achieved. Most seaport volumes of containerized goods are low as a consequence of the poor performance of the country's economy. This involves a critical study of how the economic circumstances of countries affect seaports.

Sakyi et al (2007) noted that if international trade is essential for economic and social welfare outcomes effectively promoted by improving transport and border performance, improving the standard of seaport services remains very important for the African continent, which has been plagued with lower economic and social welfare outcomes. Therefore, it is imperative to determine the impact economic conditions such as GDP, exchange rate, interest rate, taxes, supply and demand of goods, and inflation impact on seaports throughput for containerized goods in West Africa.

The literature review on emerging economies evident that little attention has been heeded to smaller emerging economies, specifically in the region of Africa. The Africa region have some of the world's biggest reserves of oil. Yet, seaports are challenging even though the region is striving to industrialize and modernize its economies. Using regression model, panel cointegration and causality analysis, there was a long-run steady-state relationship between seaport output and economic indicators of West African countries and established a positive and significant relationship between seaport and economic indicators such as GDP, and exchange rate.

Our research makes the following contribution to the extant literature; First, the research provides a comparative analysis of the relationship between the macroeconomic indicators and seaport throughput of West Africa Countries. Second, it reveals the most important areas to focus on in the attempt to enhance economic conditions among ECOWAS seaports. Last but not the least, it provides results that are more general with wider applicability by using a larger sample which to the best of our knowledge, no research has considered.

Therefore, scholars believe that, assessing the impact of economic conditions would be imperative on the Continent of Africa on Seaports.

Materials and methods

Data and Methods

The paper examined the impact of economic indicators on the throughput for containerized goods for 13 West Africa States and employed quantitative approach with the population 13 out of 16 West Africa Countries. However, the selected seaports are Port of Apapa (Nigeria), Port of Banjul (Gambia), Port of Tema (Ghana), Port of Abidjan (Cote d'Ivoire), Port of Cotonou (Benin), Port of Praia (Cape Verde), Port of Conakry (Guinea), Porto Pidjiguiti (Guinea- Bissau), Port Buchanan (Liberia), Friendship port (Mauritania), Port of Freetown (Sierra Leone), Port of Dakar (Senegal) and Lome Port (Togo). It is worthy to note that, the study focused on selecting seaport from each sampled country within the range of 100,000 – 1,000,000 TEUs based on import and export of containerized goods. The sample was based on the reason that, the countries are on the coastal line and have seaports, with accurate data on the economic variables from the World Development indicators (WDI).

Definitions of the Variables and Data Description

The annual GDP, exchange rates, interest rate, inflation, and consumer price index were obtained from the World Development Indicators (WDI). The units are expressed in US dollars. The empirical timeframe depends on data availability, but overall, the data covers the period from 2009 to 2019. In natural logarithms, and each matched cross-section observation, all variables are. This technique was used and implemented by previous researchers, such as Paul and Rabindra (2004), Beaudreau (2005), Lee (2005), Thompson (2006) and Sari and Soytas (2007), among others. Fortunately, containerized throughput into the empirical model were obtained from the selected seaports data source within the range of 100,000 – 1,000,000 TEUs based on import and export of containerized goods. In other words, although it is not possible to measure the value of containerized throughput very accurately, it is possible to obtain a fairly reliable measure of the trend from number containerized handled at the Seaports.

Panel cointegration and causality analysis

The study performs a panel unit root test before the cointegration analysis of the panel data is conducted. The analysis involves numerous studies, including those of Levine et al. (2002), Im et al. (2003) and Breitung (2000). In addition, the study follows the Maddala and Wu (1999) procedures that propose a simpler non-parametric root unit test and recommend using the statistics of Fisher-ADF and Fisher-PP. At the 5 percent significance mark, Table 1 displays the panel unit root test results. The other statistics solidly confirm that the five series (GDP, exchange rates, interest rate, inflation, and taxes) are the I (1) method, except for the UB tests from the level model with time effects and the LB variable from the Fisher-PP test without time effects. Using

these findings, the study uses the heterogeneous panel cointegration test developed by Pedroni (1999) to test for data cointegration, allowing cross-sectional interdependence with different individual results. There are two types of residual-based tests suggested by Pedroni (1999). For the first form four tests are asymptotically distributed as standard normal and are focused on pooling the inside-group regression residuals; they are the v-statistic panel., panel r-statistic, panel PP-statistic and the panel ADF-statistic.

Table 1. Panel Unit Root Test

Model	No time effects		Fixed effects	
	CTP	ECIN	CTP	ECIN
Level LL	1.08	0.43	1.51	1.43
UB	3.41	3.84	-4.18**	-3.70**
IPS	1.09	1.08	2.06	1.46
Fisher ADF	1.08	1.16	2.02	1.60
Fisher PP	0.09	0.97	2.44	1.66
First Difference				
LL	-5.95*	-7.25**	-5.14	-6.04*
UB	(-5.62)	-6.38**	-4.71*	-6.14*
IPS	(-8.00)	-10.40**	-7.09*	-9.65*
ADF	(-7.89)	-9.72**	-6.74*	-8.06*
PP	-11.98	-11.46*	-14.69**	-15.12*

All variables were in natural logarithms from the table shown above. The panel unit root tests of Levine et al. (2002), Breitung (2000) and Im et al. (2003), respectively, reflect LL, UB and IPS. The Maddala and Wu (1999) Fisher-ADF and Fisher-PP panel unit root tests respectively, reflect Fisher-ADF and Fisher-PP. The LL, UB, IPS, Fisher-ADF and Fisher-PP are testing the null non-stationary hypothesis. ** and * show statistical significance at the level of 5 percent and 10 percent, respectively. Using an asymptotic χ^2 distribution, probabilities for Fisher-type tests were computed. Asymptotic normality is considered by all other measures. However, the research objective here is to test the five economic variables for cointegration to determine if there is a long-run relationship to control for in the econometric specification.

$$Y = \beta_0 + y_u \text{GDP}_{1it} + y_u \text{EXRTs}_{2it} + y_{it} \text{INTRAT}_{3it} + y_{it} \text{INFT}_{4it} + y_{it} \text{CPI}_{5it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where Y stands for throughput for containerized goods, GDP is the Gross Domestic Product for selected countries, EXRTs is exchange rates, INTRAT is the interest rate, INFT is inflation, CPI is consumer price index of the countries. Equation (1) allows cointegrated vectors of differing magnitudes between countries, and trend-effects (d_t). These trend-effects are intended to capture any disturbances that are common across different

members of the panel, such as international business cycles. In natural logarithms, all the variables are expressed so that the throughput for containerized goods can also be represented, and the Y's are the model's parameters.

Table 2. Panel Cointegration test Findings

	No time effects	Fixed time effects
Panel Variance ratio	1.076	1.878**
Panel p	-0.243**	0.198
pp	-1.955**	-2.610**
ADF	-1.664**	1.490

The table above reports the panel cointegration estimated findings. It is worthy to note that, that the dependent variable is containerized sea port throughput. Except for the panel variance (no time effects), the panel r statistics, all other statistics significantly reject the null of no cointegration. While not for all studies, a long-run relationship is formed in order to generally obtain clear evidence of integration between these series that throughput for containerized goods and economic indicators travel together in the long-run. That is, after allowing for country-specific effects, there is a long-run steady-state relationship between seaport output and economic indicators of West African countries. The analysis will estimate this connection with this.

Using the FMOLS technique, a long-run relationship is determined for heterogeneous typically gain clear evidence of integration between these series that throughput for containerized goods and economic indicators pass together in the long-run. That is, after allowing for country-specific effects, there is a long-term steady state relationship between throughput for containerized goods and economic indicators for a cross-section of West African countries. The next step is to estimate the correlation for cointegrated panels (Pedroni, 2000). Panel FMOLS tests where the dependent variable is the throughput for containerized goods.

Table 3. Fully modified OLS estimates

Country and Port Grouping	Economic Indicators (ECI)
Benin	-0.77 (-2.99) **
Cape Verde	0.94 (3.84) **
Gambia	0.51 (3.85) **
Ghana	0.71 (1.69) *
Guinea	-0.14 (-0.65)
Guinea-Bissau	0.67 (5.69) **
Liberia	0.26 (1.41)

Mauritania	-0.06 (-0.42)
Cote d'Ivoire	0.30 (3.67) **
Nigeria	-0.08 (-0.74)
Senegal	0.03 (0.31)
Sierra Leone	0.47 (15.07) **
Togo	0.61 (1.47) *

From Table 3, all of the coefficients of economic variables are statistically significant at the 5% level, and the effect is positive. Implicit here is that a 1% increase in economic indicators such as GDP, inflation, exchange rates lead to a 0.32% increase in the number of containerized goods to be handled by respective country seaports in our sample of West Africa countries. The coefficients of economic indicators have a positive effect on throughput for some countries such as Cape Verde, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Togo, and Liberia. In general, the results of the integration test clearly show that most of the West African states have a consistent relationship between the throughput for containerized goods and economic indicators. The next step is to test the relationship for regression statistics. Research estimates regressions of the indicators effect on container port throughput in order to analyze the macroeconomic situation impact on seaport throughput. Below is the regressions equation.

$$\text{CoPT} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{GDP}_1 + \beta_2 \text{EXRTs}_2 + \beta_3 \text{INTRAT}_3 + \beta_4 \text{INFT}_4 + \beta_5 \text{CPI}_5 + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where CoPT is container port throughput, GDP is the Gross Domestic Product for the selected countries, EXTRs is exchange rates, INTRAT is the interest rate, INFT is inflation, CPI is consumer price index of the 13 sampled countries. β_0 Indicate the constant parameter of the regression model. ($\beta_1 - \beta_4$) represent the coefficients of the independent variables on the dependent variable and ε_{it} is the stochastic or error term. However, the regression model was used to ascertain the relationship between the variables. The correlation coefficient was also used to determine how independent variables interrelate with dependent variable in the study. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed to examine the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable in the regression analysis.

Conclusion

Results and findings

The table below shows the summary statistics of the variables used in the research. On average, containerized throughput increased through the various economic conditions with a percentage of 35 percent. It emanates from a range of (14.39) that stems from a minimum of (0.24) for containerized throughput and a maximum of (14.63.). The positive sign of both maximum and minimum values shows the increasing of containerized throughput in seaports in West Africa countries. On average, containerized throughput in seaports in West Africa countries improves through GDP of 46 percent. However, the mean value of exchange rate was (3.36) with a minimum value of (2.51) and maximum value of (5.2). Containerized throughput in seaports in West

Africa countries escalates as results of taxes with a mean value of 4.2 with a minimum value of (3.22) and maximum value 4.81 respectively. The average value for inflation as economic indicator improving containerized throughput in seaports in West Africa countries was (3.36), and interest rate (3.56). The summary of the findings are as follows;

Table 4. Descriptive Summary

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
CoPT	3.58	4.61	0.24	14.63
GDP	4.60	0.90	2.73	5.56
EXCR	3.36	0.82	2.51	5.2
INTR	3.56	0.65	2.52	4.54
INFT	3.38	0.65	2.12	4.61
CPI	4.20	0.58	3.22	4.81

Table 5. Correlation of Variables for Throughput and Economic indicators

	1	2	3	4	5	6
CoPT	1					
GDP	.1474**	1				
EXCR	.3651**	0.2721	1			
INTR	.2223**	0.1293	0.036	1		
INFT	.2143**	0.3068	0.300	0.2	1	
CPI	.1347**	0.549	0.540	0.3	0.343	1

From the correlation table above, there is positive relationship between the effects of economic indicators (GDP, exchange rate, interest rate, inflation and CPI) on seaport throughput. Looking at the correlation coefficients between the variables, it shows that, the signs are consistent with the literature and the study since the magnitude coefficient is less than 5. Moreover, exchange rate and interest rate are positively and highly linked which approves that, it is one of the effects of economic indicators on which seaport throughput is increased or affected. Empirically, the results show that all the discussed economic indicators effects seaport throughput implying that, it influences seaport throughput.

Model Regression

Table 6. Regression Analysis

CoPT	Std. Err.	T-Statistics	t-Value	P-Value
GDP	0.322	0.441	8.678	0.0000***

EXCR	0.233	0.200	3.863	0.0000***
INTR	0.331	0.461	9.013	0.0000***
INFT	0.32	0.329	6.381	0.0000***
CPI	0.332	0.259	5.006	0.0000***

The table above shows the model regression analysis. CoPT represents container throughput, GDP represents Gross Domestic Product, EXCR represents Exchange Rate, INTR represents Interest Rate, INFT represents Inflation, and CPI represents Capital Intensive. *** indicates 1% significance level.

From the results of regression model shown in the table below, economic indicator variables statistically and significantly affect the throughput for containerized goods regards to seaports of West Africa countries. They are positively related to containerized throughput in seaports of West Africa countries but it is imperative to note that, the positive effect of GDP, exchange rates, interest rate, inflation, and CPI on containerized throughput is consistent with prior studies (Pedroni, 2000). The results of analyzing show that the hypothesis is supported and there are positive variables between variables. The results in the regression show that in general, independent variables positively affect the containerized throughput of seaports for West Africa countries. Therefore, the independent factors increase or impact containerized throughput in seaports of West Africa countries. In this regard, the effect of GDP, exchange rate and interest rate (0.332, $P < 0.000$; 0.322; $P < 0.000$; 0.331, $P < 0.000$) on containerized throughput in seaports of West Africa countries was stronger than the rest of the independent factors.

Table 7. Results of Regression

Multiple R	R-Square	Adjusted R-squared	Standard Error of
0.545	0.545	0.514	1.57

Note: Prob>F=0.2365

Testing the relationship between study variables, statistically from the table, independent factor variables contribute to a good fit at a significance F value (0.2365), since the F value is less than 0.5). Nonetheless, the explanatory variables show that 54 percent of variations in containerized throughput for seaports in West Africa countries. Moreover, independent factor variables discussed in the research positively affect containerized throughput of seaports in West Africa countries while other economic factors not measured in the study impacts the remaining 46 percent Containerized throughput of West Africa countries.

The research adopted the procedure of Sakyi et al (2017) on economic developments through seaports throughput. From the equation, economic indicators as the explanatory variables like Gross Domestic Product (GDP), exchange rate, interest rate, inflation and taxes are regressed. Taking only into account, the findings concerning the direct effects, it is found that, Gross Domestic product and taxes have the strongest direct impact on containerized throughput of seaports. (0.332, 0000*; 0.322, 0000* respectively), which is in line with the

findings of Thoresen et al, (2004). Interest rate and inflation have a weaker but still significant direct impact on containerized throughput of seaports (0.233, 0000*, 0.32, 0000*, respectively). Concerning positive relationship between containerized throughput and macroeconomic indicators. The research question was answered and confirmed, which is in line with other researchers examined the relationships and found similar results. (Dizgah et al (2012).

However, the findings also reveal a positive relationship between containerized throughput of seaports and exchange rate. Other scholars who have conducted with these factor variables found similar results. Organizational culture is one of the indicators of the outstanding performance of employees of an organization. This implies that an increase in exchange rate or the rise of exchange rates activities will lead to an increase in containerized throughput of seaports. All the independent factor variables have a positive influence on containerized throughput of seaports which is in line with other researcher's findings.

Determining the exact relationship between throughput of containerized goods (exports and imports) and economic indicators in West Africa countries when no other variables are controlled for is certainly of considerable interest to policymakers, economists and other academic circles alike. Though its relationship between containerized goods output and economic conditions from either developed or developing country models has not typically been investigated in empirical studies, this study argues that economic conditions or indicators are indeed an important factor in containerized goods throughput. For this reason, the regression model was used to empirically re-examine long-run co-movement and the causal relationship between throughput for containerized goods for seaports and economic indicators.

Nonetheless, the study not only explores one country, but rather 13 countries selecting one seaport from each sampled country. The study uses new heterogeneous panel cointegration and panel-based error correction model techniques to re-examine the relationship because the time series data can generate inaccurate and inconsistent results with the short time spans of traditional datasets.

High economic indicators appears to come with high containerized throughput, but not the opposite. The findings provide clear evidence for both current and past economic indicators reforms that have had a substantial effect on changes on throughput for containerized goods for seaports in West African States. This implies that continuous economic indicators produce a steady increase in seaport throughput for containerized goods. Furthermore, the research established economic indicators are positively related to the throughput for containerized goods for seaports of West Africa countries are but it is imperative to note that, the positive effect of GDP, exchange rates, interest rate, inflation, and taxes are significant. The main conclusion stemming from these findings is, economic indicators are fundamental driver of increased number of throughputs for containerized goods of West Africa countries. This means that policymakers could boost economic growth in West Africa as by stimulating seaports. One-way policymakers of these countries could enhance their economic indicators such as good inflation, GDP, better and enhanced exchange rates as a catalyst by increasing good

imports and exports in order to generate higher handling of throughput. The other, which is definitely the most important, is that the government should invest in their economies by improving real GDP, as with stable economic indicators, and its path is currently led by most advanced countries.

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